
Inequality, poverty and economic growth

Robert Breunig and Omer Majeed (2019)
International Economics, forthcoming.

Key findings

We use data from 1960 to 2016 on 152 countries and examine the relationship between inequality and economic growth. We find:

- Inequality in the absence of poverty does not have a negative effect on economic growth.
- As poverty increases, the effect of inequality on economic growth becomes negative and statistically significant.
- The results suggest that governments should focus on policies which reduce poverty if they want to improve economic growth.

What we knew

- There has recently been a renewed focus on the relationship between inequality and economic growth.
- Despite popular conceptions that inequality is bad for growth, academic research is actually quite divided with some studies finding that inequality is good for growth, some finding no effect and some finding a negative effect.
- Economic theory is ambiguous as to the effect of inequality on economic growth.
 - Inequality may create incentives which encourage economic growth.
 - Unequal distribution of resources and the ensuing lack of investment in the poor may hamper economic growth.

What we do

- We use a sample that covers a longer time period and more countries than any previous study.
- We estimate cross-country growth regressions controlling for inequality, poverty, their interaction and relevant covariates such as education and investment.
- We use cutting-edge estimation techniques that deal with reverse causality and the identification of the key impacts.

What we know now

- The central findings of this paper suggest that the proposition that inequality is harmful to economic growth on its own may be too strong.
- We find that when poverty, as measured using the World Bank definition of daily income below US\$1.90, is less than about 30 per cent, the relationship between inequality and economic growth is statistically insignificant.
- As poverty increases, the effect of inequality on economic growth becomes negative and statistically significant.

What this means for policy

- Reducing inequality on its own may not improve economic growth prospects.
 - For example, simply destroying wealth at the top of the income distribution, which would reduce inequality, will not have a positive effect on economic growth prospects.
 - Tax policies which discourage economic activity and growth but reduce inequality will not have an offsetting positive effect on economic growth through the reduction of inequality.
- Poverty alleviation policies, even if they do not reduce inequality, will promote economic growth.
- There are a variety of reasons why countries might want to reduce inequality even if there is no impact on economic growth. These reasons may include inequality's impact on social cohesion and institutions.

Where to now?

- Knowing which policies work to reduce poverty is of utmost importance.
- Our study highlights the huge value that is generated by the Nobel-prize winning work of Esther Duflo and others about what types of programs actually work to reduce poverty.
- In countries such as Australia, we need much greater focus on which programs work and which don't work so that public investment in poverty reduction can be effective. Good data and high quality evaluation strategies are the key.

More information

- Get the full working paper at: https://crawford.anu.edu.au/files/uploads/crawford01_cap_anu_edu_au/2017-07/inequality.pdf or the published version at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2110701719301052>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
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